

Delamination Location and Size by Modified Acoustic Emission on Cross-ply CFRP Laminates during Compression-Compression Fatigue Loading

Christophe A. Paget (christophe.paget@airbus.com)

Airbus, NDT & Testing Technology

New Filton House

Filton, Bristol, BS99 7AR, England

Abstract

The paper deals with location and size evaluation of delamination on cross-ply CFRP panels by modified acoustic emission system called VIGILANT. The system continuously monitored the specimens loaded in compression-compression fatigue loading. The modified acoustic emission system has proved its capability in locating delamination within a location error not exceeding 30mm. Besides, the mechanical noise generated by the universal testing machine and the fretting between the CFRP plate and the anti-buckling device was successfully filtered out by the VIGILANT system. The delamination size was also assessed within good agreement.

Keywords: Acoustic emission, CFRP, fatigue, delamination

Introduction

The increasing demand in lowering maintenance costs in aeronautics contributes to the growing development of structural health monitoring systems (Klas Levin and Rolf Jarlås, 1997; Paget, 2001; Paget & Atherton, 2004; Stehmeier & Speckmann & Bolten, 2004). Such systems would insure continuous knowledge of the structural state of the monitored aircraft components, possibly allowing directed maintenance and maintenance task optimisation. Airbus has a large knowledge in structural health monitoring for well over 15 years, with a great understanding in the monitoring methods and failure assessment. The structural health monitoring system discussed in that present work is the VIGILANT system (Ultra Electronics, 2009) based on modified acoustic emission (AE) measurement. This technique provides a global monitoring of large areas with a small number of sensors. The system was extensively validated on metallic structures, and is now being evaluated on composite structures.

The aims of that study were to locate the delamination (both artificial and impact damage), investigate the acoustic emission characteristics generated by delamination. The paper shall present the experimental setup and provide the results from the AE data recorded on few specimens throughout several million fatigue-loading cycles.

Specimen description

The carbon fibre reinforced epoxy system under investigation was a commercially available prepreg from Ciba-Geigy comprising HTA carbon fibre impregnated with Fibredux 6376C. The cross-ply laminate had a stacking

sequence of $[(0_2/90_2)_{10}/0]_s$. The laminate was cured at 180°C for 120min in an autoclave at 600kPa. The laminate had a nominal fibre volume of 62% and a nominal ply thickness of 0.133mm. The specimen was a cross-ply CFRP laminate 600mm by 400mm by 10.9mm. Ultrasonic C-scanning was used to check the quality of the specimens to be tested. An anti-buckling device was designed to allow the specimens to be tested in compression-compression loading, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CFRP plate with anti-buckling device

Figure 2: C-scan of 45J impact (left) and artificial (right) delamination before loading

Two plates were tested. Plate A was impacted by a low velocity impactor to 45J, and Plate B contained an artificial

damage created by a 30mm diameter Teflon film embedded between the 6th and 7th laminate plies.

Figure 2 shows the 45J impact damage of Panel A and the artificial delamination of Panel B (30mm in diameter), before loading.

Test Setup

Twelve acoustic emission (AE) sensors and preamplifiers were surface-bounded to the plates as shown in Figure 3. Sensors/preamplifiers 1 to 6 and 7 to 12 were tuned to resonate at 150kHz and 300kHz, respectively. The 150kHz frequency was selected for being close to the plate natural frequency, allowing two “almost” non-dispersive Lamb wave modes S_0 and A_0 to propagate, as shown in Figure 4. The 300kHz frequency was chosen to simulate variable plate thickness often seen on aircraft structure resulting in having a non-optimised sensor central frequency. The results from 300kHz sensors are not discussed in this paper.

Figure 3: Acoustic emission sensors and preamplifiers

The number of sensors was purposely higher than in real application to allow studying various sensor position effect in another investigation. The sensors/preamplifiers were further connected to the damage assessment system, VIGILANT, via 50Ω coaxial cables. The VIGILANT system was setup to filter mechanical noise from the universal testing machine and the anti-buckling device, using guard sensors. The background noise threshold was then set to 41dB_{AE}, which is about 6dB above the background noise caused by the structure, testing machine and VIGILANT electronics. The compression factors were set to 20 and 100 for the normal mode (Leading Edge) and emergency mode (Peak Detection), respectively (Ultra Electronics, 2009). The system resolution on the location was set to be within 4μs in terms of time-of-flight or 28mm in terms of distance. Neither child arrays nor conditional logics were set-up in the VIGILANT due to the monitoring of a single damage only. The tick and waiting times were chosen to 7.81ms and 0.5ms, respectively (refer to

VIGILANT system user manual (Ultra Electronics, 2009)). The system was continuously monitoring the specimen excluding during the maintenance periods.

Figure 4: Dispersion curves for cross-ply CFRP plates

Table 1: Load levels

Specimens	Cycles			
	0-1M	1M-2M	2M-3M	3M-7M
Plate A	Max	-60kN	-60kN	-60kN
	Min	-600kN	-600kN	-600kN
Plate B	Max	-50kN	-55kN	-58kN
	Min	-500kN	-550kN	-580kN

The universal testing machine, shown in Figure 1, was loading the specimen in compression-compression fatigue loading, with load ratio of 10, up to a range from -60kN to -600kN insuring the generation of AE and below the expected load level for delamination growth. The loading cycle was a sinusoidal waveform at 2Hz frequency. Table 1 provides the load levels versus the load cycles for Plates A and B.

Figure 5: 12-channel VIGILANT system

Damage location

Six 150kHz sensors (Sensors 1 to 6) were used to locate the impact and artificial damage during compression-compression fatigue loading in plates A and B, respectively.

Impact delamination

Figures 6 and 7 show the location plots of acoustic emission density and amplitude for 45J impact damage (Plate A), respectively. In both figures, the delamination was located by the VIGILANT equipment within 30mm accuracy, which is an acceptable error margin in aeronautics. This was mostly due to the system resolution, set to 28mm for simplifying the data analysis, although the equipment resolution could have been reduced to 0.7mm. The recorded acoustic emission density reaches a peak of 10800 acoustic emission events near the impact damage location after 7M loading cycles.

Figure 6: AE density location; 45J-impact at dashed cross

Figure 7: Cumulative AE amplitude location; 45J-impact located at dashed cross (in Volts)

Figure 7 highlights that the delamination created by the 45J-impact does not exhibit the largest acoustic emission amplitude, but rather amplitudes or energies around 60volts. Most of high AE amplitudes were located at the plate edges, coinciding with the anti-buckling frame, as expected.

The acoustic emission sources were present at the tips of the impacted delamination, along the loading path only, where the stress level is at its highest.

Artificial delamination

Figures 8 and 9 are the location plots of AE density and amplitude recorded in Plate B containing a 30mm-diameter artificial delamination, respectively, after only 2M and 3M loading cycles. In both figures, the delamination was located within 15mm accuracy. The AE sources were situated at the tips of the artificial delamination, mainly along the loading path, as expected, due to the loading and lay-up types. The distance between the identified acoustic emission clusters was 35mm at 2M loading cycles and increased to 40mm after 3M loading cycles. The data were filtered up to 15000 AE bursts to remove the lower occurring events in order to stress to those with highest significance. Although the distance between the clusters increased with loading cycles, it is shown in Figure 17 that no delamination growth was measured. Therefore, as it stands, AE is not yet accurate enough to provide damage assessment, and further work is expected in this area.

Figure 8: AE density location at 2M (top) and 3M (bottom) cycles; Teflon film located at dashed circle

The recorded acoustic emission density reaches peaks of 8400 and 67400 acoustic emission events near the artificial damage location after 2M and 3M loading cycles,

respectively. The changing load level had most probably affected that data, but such an exponential increase was nevertheless expected, obeying laws comparatively similar to those for metallic structures. Figure 9 shows relationship behaving closely to that of the cumulative AE burst count plot in terms of damage size. Most of high AE amplitudes were located at the plate edges, coinciding with the anti-buckling frame, as expected. The amplitude recorded near the delamination was 100 and 1000 volts after 2M and 3M loading cycles, respectively.

Moreover, the VIGILANT system proved to have efficiently filtered the fretting initiated between the anti-buckling support and the CFRP plate edges, as well as the noise created by the testing machine on the anti-buckling device and specimen during fatigue loading.

Figure 9: Cumulative AE amplitude location at 2M (top) and 3M (bottom) cycles; Teflon film located at dashed circle (in Volts)

Acoustic emission characteristics

Impact delamination

Figure 10 gives the cumulative burst count versus testing time from Plate A. The constant value corresponds to testing machine stopped or monitoring system switched off, for maintenance purposes. The cumulative burst count appeared to increase by a constant rate, meaning that no structural

change has occurred during the entire loading period. This is further demonstrated by Figure 11, providing the burst rate of the recorded acoustic emission events. Indeed, the AE burst rate varied between 60 and 260 bursts per hours. An eventual structural change, such as delamination growth, would typically increase the burst rate to thousands of bursts.

Figure 10: Cumulative burst count versus time; Plate A

Figure 11: Burst count rate versus time; Plate A

Figure 12: C-scan of delamination after 7M loading cycles; Plate A

C-scanning examination of the CFRP plate A fatigued by 7M loading cycles identified no visible growth of the impacted delamination, which was once again confirmed by

the burst rate data of Figure 11. The C-scan picture of the delamination after 7M loading cycles is shown in Figure 12.

The acoustic emission amplitude was herein processed and provided on graph cumulative acoustic emission activity versus time in Figure 13. The behaviour of the cumulative amplitude was similar to that of cumulative burst.

Figure 13: Cumulative AE activity versus time; Plate A

Figure 14: First-hit sensor amplitude (dB_{AE}) versus time; Plate A

Figure 14 shows the amplitude level (in dB_{AE}) versus time. Amplitude levels related to fibre breakage or delamination growth should typically reach at least 105dB_{AE} and remain at that level as long as the damage grows or fibre breakage occurs. The figure identifies just one short event with amplitudes reaching such amplitude level.

Artificial delamination

Figure 15 gives the cumulative burst count over time. The constant value corresponds to testing machine stopped or monitoring system switched off, for maintenance purposes. The cumulative burst count appeared to increase by a steady rate, that means that a structural change might have occurred during the entire loading period. This is further demonstrated by Figure 16, providing the burst rate of the recorded acoustic emission events. Indeed, the AE burst rate

was about 100 AE burst per hour, and then increased to 540 AE bursts per hour thereafter. This rise by 5 times of the burst rate might probably be due to the change in the specimen load level, rather than damage growth, as identified below in Figure 17.

Figure 15: Cumulative burst count versus time for 3M cycles; Plate B

Figure 16: Burst count rate versus time for 3M cycles; Plate B

Figure 17: C-scan of Plate-B delamination after 3M cycles

The acoustic emission amplitude was herein analysed and the results are given on the graph cumulative acoustic emission activity versus time of Figure 18. The behaviour of

the cumulative amplitude was similar to that of cumulative burst. Figure 19 shows the amplitude level (in dB_{AE}) versus time. The figure identifies acoustic emission events of high amplitudes on the later portion of the test, again probably caused by the load increased for the same period.

Figure 18: Cumulative AE activity versus time after 3M cycles; Plate B

Figure 19: First-hit sensor amplitude (dB_{AE}) versus time; Plate B

Conclusions

The present study emphasised on the ability for the VIGILANT system to locate delamination (impacted or artificial) within 30mm on CFRP cross-ply laminates subjected to fatigue loading. Most of the acoustic emission sources were situated at the tips of the delamination along the loading axis, coinciding with the stress concentration areas. The VIGILANT system demonstrated that the delamination was generating a relatively constant rate of acoustic emission events during compression-compression loading as long as the delamination does not grow. The VIGILANT system has successfully filtered external acoustic emission initiated by the rig or fixtures throughout the whole testing period, allowing the system to be used on ground structural tests to monitor CFRP specimens.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to acknowledge Dr Klas Levin for his support in carrying out the experiments. The author thank the European Commission for co-funding this work via the SMIST project

References

Levin K. & Jarlås R. (1997). Vulnerability of embedded EFPI-sensors to low-energy impacts. *Smart Material and Structures*, 6 (3).

Paget C. A. (2001). *Active Health Monitoring of Composites by Embedded Piezoceramic Transducers* (Doctoral Thesis, Report 2001-25). Department of Aeronautics, The Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden.

Paget C. A. & Atherton K. J. (2004). Damage Assessment in a Full-Scale Aircraft Wing by Modified Acoustic Emission. *Proceedings of the 2nd European Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring* (pp. 382-7), Munich, Germany.

Stehmeier H. & Speckmann H. & Bolten J. (2004). Comparative Vacuum Monitoring (CVM) Monitoring of fatigue cracking in aircraft structures. *Proceedings of the 2nd European Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring*, Munich, Germany.

Ultra Electronics Ltd (2009), User Manual, Bridport Road, Greenford, US6 8UA, England.